

TERASUN

Towards Terawatt Production of c-Si Solar Photovoltaics

D6.5 Report on clustering and alignment activities with other funded initiatives M18

**Funded by
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Project Profile

Table 1 Key figures of the TERASUN project.

Programme	Horizon Europe
Call	HORIZON-CL5-2023-D3-02
Topic	HORIZON-CL5-2023-D3-02-11
Number	101147545
Acronym	TERASUN
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Duration	36 months
Type of action	HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions
Granting authority	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
Coordinator	IDENER

TERASUN Consortium Partners

Table 2 List of partners in the TERASUN project including acronym and country.

#	Partner	Short	CO
1	IDENER R&D AGRUPACION DE INTERES ECONOMICO	IDE	ES
2	Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy Systems	ISE	DE
3	PV2+	PV2+	DE
4	Commissariat à l'énergie atomique et aux énergies alternatives	CEA	FR
5	Technische Universiteit Delft	TUD	NL
6	RINA Consulting – Centro Sviluppo Materiali SPA	RINA-CSM	IT
7	Fyzikalni Ustav AV CR V.V.I.	FZU	CZ

		Özko, TUD	
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Executive Summary

The deliverable D6.5 “Report on clustering and alignment activities with other funded initiatives,” describes the actions undertaken by the Terasun consortium to establish synergies with other EU-funded projects and initiatives during the first 18 months of the project. These activities are part of WP6 (Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation) and aim to maximize the impact of Terasun by fostering collaboration, knowledge exchange, and joint dissemination within the European photovoltaic (PV) innovation ecosystem.

TERASUN has implemented a structured mapping of relevant EU-funded initiatives, identifying projects with overlapping objectives and potential for collaboration. A key outcome of this process is the creation of the **SMARTIES Cluster** (Sustainable Materials And Research Towards Innovative Engineering Solutions for Silicon Solar Cells), which brings together three Horizon Europe projects, **TERASUN**, **BURST**, and **SILEAN**, funded under the same call. The cluster provides a formal framework for joint activities, including coordinated dissemination, technical workshops, and shared communication tools. The first SMARTIES workshop, held online in February 2025, successfully gathered 74 participants from research, industry, and policy sectors, demonstrating strong interest and validating the cluster approach.

In addition, the organization of new workshops are under discussion and evaluation within SMARTIES cluster and will be described in the updated version of this deliverable.

Beyond SMARTIES, Terasun aims also to initiate links with additional projects such as SEAMLESS-PV, EVERPV, RETRIEVE, SOLARIS, EMPOWER, and SHINE PV, which address complementary aspects of PV technology development, recycling, and manufacturing scalability. These collaborations could help to accelerate technology transfer, promote interoperability, and strengthen Europe’s capacity to deploy sustainable PV solutions at scale.

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Table of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
AZO	Aluminium-doped Zinc Oxide
CA	Consortium Agreement
CINEA	EU Climate, Environment and Infrastructure Executive Agency
c-Si	Crystalline silicon
DMP	Data Management Plan
DST	Decision Support Tool
DV	Deliverable
EB	Executive Board
EC	European Commission
FBC	Front-back contacted
GA	Grant Agreement
GeA	General Assembly
IBC	Interdigitated back-contacted
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
LEAR	Legal Entity Appointed Representative
PC	Project Coordinator
PMP	Project Management Plan
PMP	Project Management Plan
PO	Project Officer
RP1, RP2	Reporting Period 1 and 2
SHJ	Silicon Heterojunction
SnOx	Tin Oxide
SO	Specific Objective
TCO	Transparent Conductive Oxide
Teams	Microsoft Teams
TL	Task Leader
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

1. Introduction

1.1. Objective

The purpose of this deliverable is to present the progress achieved under T6.5, which focuses on establishing synergies with other EU-funded projects. At M18 the first version has been developed and will be updated at M36 with additional T6.5 activities.

This task is designed to enhance the impact of Terasun by creating meaningful connections with other initiatives funded under Horizon Europe (HE) or other European programs. By fostering collaboration, the consortium aims to accelerate technology transfer, amplify dissemination efforts, and strengthen the European photovoltaic innovation ecosystem. The work emphasizes cooperation with sister projects BRUST, SiLEAN and other relevant projects, which address advanced manufacturing, circularity, and recycling challenges, to build new collaboration routes with Terasun. These objectives are fully aligned with Terasun overarching ambition to enable terawatt-scale production of crystalline silicon solar photovoltaics in a sustainable and cost-effective manner.

1.2. Scope

This report covers the clustering and alignment activities conducted by the Terasun consortium during the first eighteen months of the project. It describes

- the strategic approach adopted to identify relevant projects;
- the creation of the SMARTIES Cluster with sister projects BURST and SiLEAN;
- the organization of joint activities such as logos, online collaboration tools, and the first SMARTIES workshop; and
- the identification of additional projects to engage for synergies, highlighting their relevance to Terasun objectives.

Furthermore, the deliverable summarizes the early results and added value generated through these interactions, demonstrating how collaboration has strengthened dissemination, technical alignment, and exploitation strategies for Terasun project.

The scope of this deliverable, therefore, is focused on reporting and documenting the progress of clustering and synergy-building activities; and highlight the impact of networking and collaboration efforts within the broader European PV research and innovation landscape.

2. TERASUN impact and projects mapping for synergies

To maximize the impact of TERASUN's activities, the project is implementing a systematic process to identify and develop synergies with other initiatives funded by EU. This work is based on the recognition of several H2020, HE and other EU funded projects that are currently addressing similar or complementary challenges to those of TERASUN.

Establishing connections with these initiatives will significantly strengthen the value of TERASUN work by accelerating technology transfer and contributing to a wider community that can support the uptake of project results beyond the end of the project duration. Synergies have the potential to increase the visibility of TERASUN within the scientific, industry, and policy areas, promote interoperability between technological solutions, facilitate access to existing expertise and infrastructures, and support the broader dissemination of shared standards, protocols and methodological approaches.

To identify the most relevant projects for collaboration, the consortium conducted a mapping of EU funded projects based on multiple sources. On one side, project funded under the same call has been identified and grouped into "SMARTIES" (Sustainable Materials And Research Towards Innovative Engineering Solutions for Silicon Solar Cells): a cluster of projects selected based on the alignment of core objectives. This clustering helps to define collaboration pathways. Joint activities within the cluster can include dissemination, organization of technical workshops and knowledge sharing events, participation in EU energy and innovation platforms, exchange of technical results and the assessment of joint exploitation opportunities, particularly in industrial domains where technological maturity enables future scalability.

At the same time, several TERASUN partners are already involved in EU-funded initiatives related to advanced solar materials, high-temperature components, circularity, and digital manufacturing. These existing collaborations provide a valuable starting point for building synergies, as they offer access to established networks, shared knowledge, and relevant infrastructures. Starting from these connections, TERASUN can initiate joint activities such as technical exchanges, shared dissemination actions, and participation in clustering events, strengthening the overall impact of the project.

The project mapping activity will evolve throughout the duration of TERASUN, updating the landscape of European initiatives with which collaboration could be fostered. This will strengthen TERASUN contribution to the wider innovation ecosystem for advanced solar technologies, supporting key EU priorities such as the European Green Deal, the Fit for 55 package, and the European strategy for sustainable and secure energy.

3. Collaboration with sister projects – SMARTIES

3.1. SMARTIES projects and other collaborations with the cluster

TERASUN is part of the SMARTIES Cluster (Sustainable Materials And Research Towards Innovative Engineering Solutions for Silicon Solar Cells), which brings together three Horizon Europe projects funded under the call HORIZON-CL5-2023-02-11, with the common aim of strengthening the European crystalline silicon (c-Si) photovoltaic ecosystem.

Within this cluster, TERASUN collaborates closely with its sister projects:

- **BURST (Breaking Limits Using Record Enabling Silicon Technology With Photonic Management), coordinated by the Institute for Solar Energy Research in Hamelin (ISFH).**

Brief description: The [BURST](#) project aims to enhance the power conversion efficiency of interdigitated back-contact (IBC) c-Si technology by achieving efficiencies of at least 26% with thin cells and 27% with thick cells, without relying on critical materials like indium or silver. The project focuses on advanced light management, superior passivation schemes, and Ag-free metallization to maximize light absorption and prevent recombination. The high-efficiency BURST cells will be assembled into mini-modules, with detailed analysis of costs, environmental impact, supply security, and circularity to demonstrate the technology's advantages in relevant environments.

- **SiLEAN (Silicon solar cells with Low Environmental footprint and Advanced interfaces), coordinated by the Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH.**

Brief description: To meet the growing energy demand, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, and lower electricity costs, highly efficient and cost-effective photovoltaic (PV) technologies with low carbon footprints are essential. [SiLEAN](#) is a 3-year project addressing key challenges such as the high energy and material requirements for Si wafer manufacturing, limited current generation, and the use of scarce materials like silver, bismuth, and indium. In the project, a lean process chain will be developed for the next generation of silicon heterojunction (SHJ) solar cells. Our strategy involves utilizing epitaxially-grown wafers that require less energy, developing alternatives to the highly absorptive hydrogenated amorphous silicon for passivation and carrier-selective contacts, creating indium-free contact layers and silver-free metallization concepts, and implementing bismuth-free interconnection methods. Our goal is to achieve solar cell efficiencies greater than 25.5% and module efficiencies over 23.5%, while reducing Si wafer and contacting costs by 50% and lowering the carbon footprint by up to 75%.

Thanks to this formal cluster structure, the three projects organize joint dissemination and communication activities to exchange knowledge and technical results, amplify their impact, and strategically align research goals.

The first SMARTIES online workshop was held on February 20th, 2025. The event has been organized by the SMARTIES consortium, in which TERASUN and its sister projects are working to maximize synergies and collaboration on sustainable materials and solutions for silicon solar cells related topics. The joint online workshop entitled “Advanced concepts for high efficiency crystalline silicon technology,” which gathered 74 participants from research, industry, and policy communities. The workshop provided an opportunity to present the objectives and progress of each project, discuss synergies, and explore challenges and opportunities for European PV technologies. It included project presentations, a moderated Q&A session, and a panel discussion on long-term research strategies, with contributions from the European Commission, ETIP PV, and leading research institutes. This event represented a first concrete step in fostering collaboration within the SMARTIES Cluster and increasing visibility of the projects’ complementary innovations.

In this event, not only SMARTIES Cluster projects were presented but also:

- **PEPPERONI (Pilot line for European Production of PEROvskite-Silicon taNdem modules on Industrial scale), coordinated by the Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin (HZB).**

Brief description: The EU-funded PEPPERONI project will address the barriers concerning tandem perovskite-silicon solar cell technology. PEPPERONI key goals are to demonstrate 26 % more efficient modules on an industrial scale, develop fabrication processes for high-volume manufacturing and extend operational stability beyond 30 years to meet market expectations. A pilot line focused on producing silicon-perovskite tandem solar cells will be established in Germany by 2026 and large-scale Gigawatt-capable production is expected before 2030.

3.2. SMARTIES collaboration approach

Building on the SMARTIES Cluster collaboration, TERASUN is planning a proactive approach to maximize collective dissemination with its sister projects, SILEAN and BURST. The proposed initiative is structured in two phases.

The first phase will be an online workshop aimed at presenting the three projects collectively to relevant stakeholders. This virtual event will serve to raise awareness, highlight the complementary strengths of each project, and generate initial interest within the European PV community.

The second phase will involve a physical, in-person workshop, ideally integrated into a major photovoltaic conference. One promising opportunity is the EU-PVSEC conference in September 2027, which provides sufficient lead time for careful planning and alignment. This event will allow for more in-depth technical exchanges, networking, and dissemination of project results to a broad audience, including industry representatives, policymakers, and research organizations.

This joint dissemination initiative directly supports the objectives of T6.5 (Synergies with EU-funded projects) and T6.3 (Dissemination, led by IDE). By coordinating these activities early, TERASUN aims to facilitate smoother collaboration, enhance the visibility of the SMARTIES Cluster, and maximize the collective impact of the three projects on the European solar energy ecosystem.

4. Consortium partner links & other existing collaborations

In this section additional relevant projects active in the same destination of TERASUN have been identified as potential sister projects with TERASUN. First the relevance and complementarities between these projects and TERASUN have been identified to facilitate their engagement and synergies.

4.1. IBC4EU – overview and relevance to our objectives

IBC4EU – “Piloting novel cost-competitive bifacial IBC technology for vertical integrated European GW scale PV production value chain” (GA)

Brief description: The IBC4EU project will develop cost effective and sustainable bifacial interdigitated back contact (IBC) solar cell and module technology on pilot line level. Based on business cases from the whole value chain – ingot, wafer, cell and module – we will demonstrate that IBC technology is the most promising choice for a fast launch of GW scale PV production in the EU. Cost competitiveness not only against future heterojunction (HJT) and Tunnel oxide passivated contact (TOPCon) technology but also present-day PERC and PERC technology will be demonstrated for the polyZEBRA and POLO IBC cell designs.

Relevance to TERASUN: IBC4EU delivers techno-economic data, process comparisons and cost-of-ownership analyses that could help contextualise TERASUN innovation pathways and future scale up. The project end-to-end value-chain approach also could support TERASUN scale-up strategy, particularly regarding manufacturing integration, supply-chain alignment and competitiveness of European PV production.

4.2. SEAMLESS-PV – overview and relevance to our objectives

SEAMLESS-PV – “Development of advanced manufacturing equipment and processes aimed at the seamless integration of multifunctional PV solutions, enabling the deployment of IPV sectors” (GA: 101096126)

Brief description: [SEAMLESS-PV](#) is a Horizon Europe Innovation Action that develops manufacturing equipment, processes and final products to enable the wider deployment of integrated photovoltaics (IPV) across building façades, noise barriers, vehicles and agrivoltaics systems. The project coordinates pilot-line demonstrations and market-facing demo cases while combining materials research, process design and sustainability assessment to ensure that new IPV solutions meet regulatory, architectural and lifecycle requirements. SEAMLESS-PV organizes training and stakeholder events (for example IPV conferences and SOLARCHITECTURE courses) to speed architectural and industrial uptake and to define market strategies

for multifunctional PV products. The initiative runs demonstrators and exploitation actions aimed at bridging research outputs to industrial manufacturing and policy recommendations, and it explicitly targets integration challenges such as mechanical embedding, aesthetics, durability and standards compliance. SEAMLESS-PV therefore works across the full chain from equipment design to commercial roll-out of IPV products.

Relevance to TERASUN objectives: SEAMLESS-PV direct experience with pilot lines, integration of PV into novel form-factors and market uptake strategies complements TERASUN cell and module-level innovations by informing realistic packaging, reliability and productization routes for SHJ-based modules intended for building or vehicle integration. Insights into IPV mechanical requirements, long-term durability testing and sustainability metrics from SEAMLESS-PV can guide TERASUN when qualifying new materials (e.g., indium-free TCOs or alternative metallization) and designing modules for real installation contexts.

4.3. EVERPV – overview and relevance to our objectives

EVERPV – “Highly efficient delamination technologies to recover and reuse metals, glass, polymers from end-of-life photovoltaic panels” (GA: 101122208)

Brief description: [EVERPV](#) is a three-year Horizon Europe project focused on developing and demonstrating sustainable, low-cost recycling solutions for end-of-life solar panels and accelerating circular value chains for PV waste in the EU. The consortium brings together partners across the value chain, including recyclers, research institutes and PV panel manufacturers, to pilot and optimize emerging mechanical, thermal and chemical recycling techniques that recover glass, silicon, metals and polymer fractions at improved yield and quality. EVERPV places emphasis on reducing the environmental footprint and the economic cost of recycling while creating business models and collaboration frameworks that link feedstock collection to high-value reuse streams. By validating processes at pilot scale and disseminating results, EVERPV seeks to help policy makers and industry to adopt circular practices that reduce raw-material dependency and create domestic supply options for recovered PV constituents.

Relevance to TERASUN objectives: TERASUN’s ambition to scale SHJ manufacturing and to substitute or remove critical materials (e.g., indium, silver) requires robust lifecycle and supply-security planning. In this sense, EVERPV validated recycling routes and circular business cases could help TERASUN quantify how recovered silicon, glass and metals could feed back into high-throughput production. EVERPV outputs reduce feedstock risk and strengthen the sustainability argument for TERASUN material-substitution and high-volume strategies.

4.4. RETRIEVE – overview and relevance to our objectives

RETRIEVE – “Reintegration of photovoltaic panel waste back into manufacturing as high-value products” (GA: 101122332)

Brief description: [RETRIEVE](#) is a Horizon Europe Innovation Action that aims to upcycle end-of-life PV modules and production waste into materials that meet the specifications required for new module manufacturing. The project develops modular, cost-effective dismantling and recycling technologies that recover glass to PV standards, purify silicon to solar grade, extract silver and other metals at high yield, and valorise polymer streams, with the goal of demonstrating closed-loop reintegration of recycled inputs into European production. RETRIEVE also builds digital tools and market analyses, including PV datasets and product passport prototypes, and prepares business cases to enable commercial uptake of recycled-content materials. The project combines technical pilots with supply-chain and policy work to make circular PV manufacturing economically viable and reduce Europe dependence on imported raw materials.

Relevance to TERASUN objectives: By proving routes to re-introduce high-quality recycled silicon, glass and metals into the PV supply chain, RETRIEVE could directly support TERASUN strategy to lower material bottlenecks and secure feedstock for terawatt-scale SHJ production. RETRIEVE purification targets, digital traceability outputs and market cases can help TERASUN quantify circularity gains, feedstock availability and cost reductions that are crucial when designing indium-free TCOs, silver-reduced metallization or other substitute material strategies.

4.5. Other relevant 2024 Horizon calls and funded projects

4.5.1. HORIZON-CL5-2024-D3-02-07 (CSA) – SOLARIS, overview and relevance to our objectives

SOLARIS – “Supporting optimisation of photovoltaic resource efficiency and sustainability” (GA: 101235545)

Brief description: [SOLARIS](#) is a Coordination and Support Action created to support optimization of photovoltaic resource efficiency and sustainability across the entire PV lifecycle. The project collects and harmonizes data on material supply risks, recycling potential and environmental impacts, and builds tools, guidelines and policy-relevant recommendations to steer a more circular and resource-efficient European PV sector. SOLARIS focuses on stakeholder engagement and knowledge-sharing between industry, research and policy, aiming to produce roadmaps and governance measures that lower systemic risks for large-scale PV deployment while maximizing resource efficiency. SOLARIS therefore operates at the intersection of data, policy and sector coordination rather than delivering manufacturing pilots.

Relevance to TERASUN objectives: SOLARIS lifecycle data, resource-risk analyses and policy guidance can validate and amplify TERASUN technical choices by situating them within EU-level circularity and material-security roadmaps; its outputs can help showing regulators and purchasers how TERASUN innovations reduce dependency on critical imports and improve the environmental profile of SHJ manufacturing. For TERASUN exploitation and impact work, SOLARIS could provide the sectoral context and evidence needed to support uptake and investments at scale.

4.5.2. HORIZON-CL5-2024-D3-01-01 (IA) - EMPOWER overview and relevance to our objectives

EMPOWER – “Alternative processes and equipment for advanced manufacturing of PV technologies to boost the European energy independence” (GA: 101172767)

Brief description: [EMPOWER](#) is a Horizon Europe initiative aimed at developing alternative equipment, modular manufacturing concepts and process flows to lower capital and operational costs while strengthening European manufacturing resilience in the PV sector. The project brings together equipment suppliers, manufacturers and researchers to demonstrate new process routes and industrially relevant technologies that make cell and module production cheaper, more flexible and easier to scale. EMPOWER emphasizes modular tool chains and scalable pilot demonstrations and works on the business and readiness aspects required to translate pilot demonstration into industrial deployments. The project therefore targets manufacturing system innovation rather than a single cell-technology, seeking durable reductions in cost of ownership and barriers to entry for European production.

Relevance to TERASUN objectives: EMPOWER focuses on alternative, low-CAPEX process equipment and modular production lines is highly relevant to TERASUN goal of making SHJ routes terawatt-scalable. Lessons from EMPOWER on equipment architecture, throughput scaling and cost modelling could help TERASUN select industrially viable process steps and plan factory integration that minimizes capital risk. EMPOWER piloting experience therefore could complement TERASUN cell-level R&D by translating promising lab processes into manufacturable solutions.

4.5.3. 4.1.3. HORIZON-CL5-2024-D3-01-01 (IA) - SHINE PV overview and relevance to our objectives

SHINE PV – “Sustainable, High-throughput, Industry-ready, Next-generation technology for European manufacturing leadership in PV” (GA: 101172902)

Brief description: [SHINE PV](#) is a Horizon Innovation Action that targets high-throughput, industry-ready manufacturing technologies for next-generation silicon heterojunction (SHJ) and related cell concepts. The project aims to demonstrate industrially viable alternatives to costly materials and processes, including strategies for replacing silver with copper metallization, improving post-processing and interconnection methods, and integrating Industry-4.0 features into the production chain, with pilots delivered at TRL7-level. SHINE PV is a multi-partner industrial consortium validating process flows for

reduction cost of ownership while maintaining or improving cell performance, and it explicitly pursues measures that shorten the path to large-scale European production capacities.

Relevance to Terasun objectives: SHINE PV pilot demonstrations of copper metallization, advanced post-process flows, and high-throughput interconnection techniques could provide direct technical and industrial benchmarks that Terasun could adopt or adapt when scaling its SHJ innovations. Outcomes from SHINE PV reduce technical uncertainty around metallization choices, throughput impacts and integration with high-speed module assembly. The overlap in goals of replacing critical materials and raising TRL of SHJ-compatible equipment could mean learnings for both SHINE PV and Terasun are easily actionable for the common path to terawatt production.

5. Collaboration routes and joint activities

In this section activities conducted in Task 6.5 in the first eighteen months of the projects are summarised. Collaboration routes have been identified and joint events and workshop successfully organized. Future activities planned for the second half of the project are also outlined.

5.1. Joint online tools and visual identity

To establish a structured and coherent collaboration framework between TERASUN and its sister projects, a dedicated series of online coordination meetings has been organised. These meetings, which involve project coordinators and/or dissemination and exploitation (D&E) leaders from each participating project, have served as a platform to align expectations, clarify communication channels, and identify shared priorities for joint action.

One of the first collective decisions from these discussions concerns the development of a common name and logo to easily identify the cluster of projects. This shared logo is intended to strengthen cross-project visibility and facilitate recognition of the cluster as a unified research and innovation initiative within the European PV landscape.

As such the name “Sustainable Materials And Research Towards Innovative Engineering Solutions for Silicon Solar Cells,” acronym “SMARTIES” and dedicated logo have been developed.

Figure 1 SMARTIES logo

In parallel, the projects have agreed to set up joint online tools that support day-to-day collaboration and long-term knowledge sharing. These include shared workspaces for documentation exchange, common event calendars, a coordinated dissemination tracker. The objective is to build an interconnected digital environment that not only streamlines internal coordination but also facilitate the external

communication of achievements, ensuring that stakeholders can easily access coherent and complementary information across all cluster projects. Therefore, a Teams shared folder has been indeed set up by IDENER.

Moreover, to enhance the cross-visibility and cross-dissemination a dedicated page in Terasun webpage has been developed to describe SMARTIES activities, which can be found at [Cluster – Terasun](#). In this page a brief description of the sister projects, link to their website and coordinator contacts are available. Similarly, Terasun is visible in BRUST ([SMARTIES Cluster](#)) and SILEAN ([Cluster Projects - SiLEAN](#)) website.

Moreover, the engagement with additional projects, as the one already identified in this deliverable, will be sought to enlarge the SMARTIES cluster consortium and cross-visibility pool.

5.2. Joint workshop organized (M9)

In addition to strengthening cross-visibility, Terasun and the other SMARTIES cluster participants have collaborated closely on the organisation of a series of joint thematic workshops addressing cross-cutting challenges relevant to all projects. These workshops aim to provide a shared platform for exchanging technical insights, disseminating early results, and engaging with broader stakeholders from industry, academia, and policy. They represent one of the main mechanisms through which the cluster ensures continuous knowledge flow and alignment across its diverse project activities.

The first event was held on the February 20th, 2025, which is M9 for Terasun project. To maximise accessibility and encourage participation from a wide audience, including researchers, industrial actors, policy representatives and other EU-funded initiatives, the event was organised fully online. This format enabled broad outreach beyond the immediate consortium partners and ensured the inclusion of stakeholders who may not have been able to attend an in-person event.

The workshop title is “Advanced concepts for high efficiency crystalline Silicon technology: how to ensure affordability, security of supply and sustainability in PV technologies.” A digital flyer was developed (Figure 2) and shared on Terasun website ([SMARTIES workshop on Advanced concepts for high efficiency c-Si technology – Terasun](#)), social media platforms, as well as among Terasun and SMARTIES partners, respective networks and potential stakeholders.

SMARTIES EU Cluster:
Sustainable Materials And Research Towards
Innovative Engineering Solutions for Silicon Solar Cells

**SAVE THE DATE FOR THE
Online Workshop dedicated to
Advanced concepts for high efficiency
crystalline Silicon technology: how to ensure
affordability, security of supply and
sustainability of PV technologies**

**February 20th 2025
9 to 12 am CET**

- Learn more about European initiatives on innovative PV technologies
- Discuss sustainability, affordability of PV systems in Europe with field experts
- Learn from researchers, industries and policy makers about the challenges for PV sustainability

jointly organised by

 SiLEAN

 **Funded by
the European Union** **Registration will open in January 2025**

Figure 2 Flyer of the first SMARTIES workshop - “Advanced concepts for high efficiency crystalline Silicon technology: how to ensure affordability, security of supply and sustainability in PV technologies”.

Attendance was monitored through an online registration system, ensuring accurate tracking of outreach impact. The event successfully attracted 82 registrations and 74 active participants, reflecting strong interest in the workshop theme and confirming the value of coordinated dissemination within the cluster.

The workshop agenda was jointly defined during a dedicated SMARTIES cluster meeting, ensuring balanced representation from all organising projects. A specific dissemination segment was included for each contributing project, allowing them to introduce their objectives, preliminary findings and forthcoming activities. In addition, the workshop included an open panel discussion featuring project coordinators alongside representatives from the European Commission, Solar Power Europe, and the ETIP PV partnership. This interactive session fostered strategic dialogue on the challenges and opportunities facing Europe’s PV industry and highlighted the complementary contributions of the SMARTIES projects to EU solar-industrial objectives.

Slot	Topic	Speaker
9.00 – 9.05	Presentation of the agenda	Udo Römer – ISFH Johannes Seif – IDENER Karsten Bittkau – FZ JÜLICH
9.05 – 9.25	EU funding policy to PV projects and expected impacts	Mrs. Maria Getsiou – European Commission
9.25 – 9.45	Co-programmed partnership for Solar PV	Delfina Munoz – ETIP PV
9.45 – 10.05	BURST project in a nutshell	Udo Römer – ISFH
10.05 – 10.25	TERASUN project in a nutshell	Johannes Seif – IDENER
10.25 – 10.35	<i>Coffee break & stretching legs</i>	–
10.35 – 10.55	SILEAN project in a nutshell	Karsten Bittkau – FZ JÜLICH
10.55 – 11.15	Pepperoni project in a nutshell	Bernd Stannowski – HZB
11.15 – 11.35	Q&A on presentations Moderated by Achim Woyte, CINEA	Udo Römer – ISFH Johannes Seif – IDENER Karsten Bittkau – FZ JÜLICH Bernd Stannowski – HZB
11.35 – 12.00	Panel discussion on longer term European research strategy Moderated by Achim Woyte, CINEA	Bernd Stannowski – HZB Maria Getsiou – European Commission Claire Morin – Solar Power Europe Ralf Preu – ETIP PV

Figure 3 Agenda of the first SMARTIES workshop - “Advanced concepts for high efficiency crystalline Silicon technology: how to ensure affordability, security of supply and sustainability in PV technologies”.

The involvement of this high-level panel and of different speakers is a direct result of the collaboration and joint effort present within SMARTIES cluster.

5.3. Technical collaborations activities

Both TERASUN and BURST projects are interested in maximization of light absorption in c-Si wafer using advanced light management schemes. In particular, the development of plasma-based nano-structuring of the silicon surface, which is called black silicon (b-Si) is involved in both projects. TUD developed the process on 4” round wafers. To scale up to M2-size wafers, CEA provided with double side textured M2 size wafers for both projects. After upscaling optimization, sample exchange between TUD and CEA & ISE for TERASUN, and TUD and CEA & ISFH has been initiated for passivation of the nano-structured surfaces, namely b-Si.

5.4. Future joint workshop under definition

Based on the success of our first joint workshop, Terasun, together with the SMARTIES partners, is currently planning to organize a second event. Discussions are ongoing and both online and in-person initiatives are being discussed.

One possibility would be to have a second online event in March 2026 and an in-person event in September 2027. However, these proposals are still under discussion within the respective SMARTIES consortia.

6. Early results and added value for the consortium

During the first months of work in T6.5 and with SMARTIES cluster, the collaboration has already generated a set of tangible early results that demonstrate the value of structured interaction between Terasun and its sister projects. Although each project focuses on different technological or strategic aspects of the European PV value chain, the exchange facilitated through regular coordination meetings, joint communication activities, and thematic workshops has enabled a continuous flow of information that benefits all partners involved.

An early achievement lies in the harmonization of communication practices. This effort has strengthened the external visibility of the cluster. The adoption of joint online tools and shared digital workspaces has further enhanced this cooperation, creating a collaborative environment where documents, announcements and event planning resources can be exchanged smoothly and in real time.

Another significant outcome is the successful organisation of the first SMARTIES workshop in February 2025, which offered an opportunity for the projects to present their objectives, initial results and strategic direction. This event not only amplified the visibility of the cluster but also served as an early test of coordinated dissemination and audience engagement. Through the contributions of invited experts, industrial associations and EU representatives, the workshop generated valuable insights into market needs, policy expectations and technological priorities for next-generation PV manufacturing, insights that Terasun has already begun integrating into its own dissemination planning and long-term exploitation strategy.

Beyond dissemination, early interactions have also catalysed synergies between technical developments across the different projects. Exchanges on material development strategies, circularity considerations, and common manufacturing challenges have helped identify complementary research directions and avoid potential duplication of effort. In particular, the collaboration between Terasun and BRUST on passivation routes is a tangible result of this collaboration approach. This early-phase alignment increases the likelihood that the cluster will produce mutually reinforcing results, improving the overall impact of each project and strengthening the European PV innovation landscape.

These early achievements demonstrate that the cluster approach is already delivering meaningful added value for the Terasun consortium. The project gains broader visibility, access to external networks, and enriched technical perspectives, while also contributing its own expertise in SHJ innovation and terawatt-scale production challenges to the collective intelligence of the cluster. The collaboration ensures that Terasun advances are fully immersed within wider European efforts to improve affordability, sustainability and supply-chain resilience in PV technologies.

The early results presented in this document mark only the beginning of a collaboration that is expected to deepen and expand over the course of the projects, ultimately reinforcing Europe's capacity to innovate and lead in next-generation photovoltaic technologies.